

Infrared Photon Discrimination of Lung Cancer Cells

G. C. Giakos [1], S. Shrestha [1], J. Petermann [1],
C. Narayan [2], S. Marotta [2], A. Despande [2],
J. Syms [3], T. Farrahi, [1], A. Blinzler [2]

[1] Dept. of Electrical and Computer Engineering,
[2] Dept. of Biomedical Engineering
[3] Dept. of Physics
The University of Akron
Akron Ohio, 44325, USA

R. H. Picard [4], W. Inbody [5], Phan D. Dao [5]
P. N. Crabtree [5], Patrick J. McNicholl [5]

[4] ARCON Corporation, Waltham, MA 02451, USA
[5] Air Force Research Laboratory,
Space Vehicles Directorate
Kirtland AFB, NM 87111, USA

L. Zhang [6], A. Zhou [6]
[6] Department of Chemistry
Cleveland State University
Cleveland, OH. 44115, USA

M. Zervakis [7], M.G. Kounelakis [7], E.S. Bei [7],
G. Livanos [7]

[7] Department of Electronic Engineering
Technical University of Crete
Chania, P.C. 73100, Crete, Greece

Abstract— The objective of this study is to explore the polarimetric phenomenology of near infrared light interaction with healthy and lung cancer monolayer cells by using efficient polarimetric transmission detection techniques. Preliminary results indicate that enhanced discrimination between normal and different types of lung cancer cell stages can be achieved based on their transmitted intensities and depolarization properties of the cells. Specifically, the sizes of the nuclei of the cancer cells and the nucleus-to-cytoplasmic ratios appear to have potential impact on the detected polarimetric signatures leading to enhanced discrimination of lung cancer cells.

Keywords- Polarimetric phenomenology, Near infrared light, nuclei size, nucleus-to-cytoplasmic ratio, Lung squamous carcinoma, Adenocarcinoma, Mixture of cancer cells, Efficient discrimination, Polarization signatures

I. INTRODUCTION

THE purpose of this study is to develop efficient and reliable techniques for early identification and discrimination of precancerous and cancerous lung cells that can lead to accurate diagnosis and treatment of lung cancer. Early detection of lung cancer is of paramount significance.

Cancer cells can be divided into two types: Small cell lung cancer (SCLC) and non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC). About 80% of the cases are diagnosed with NSCLC.

The common detection techniques for lung cancer are classical imaging techniques like chest radiography (film or digital) and computed tomography (CT). When compared to classical radiography, digital radiography provides better contrast resolution with equal or better spatial resolution [1]; however, these techniques still do not provide meaningful

imaging information that can be utilized towards the early detection of tumors. On the other hand, low-dose, spiral / helical CT can detect earlier stages of cancer 6-10 times more frequently than radiographic imaging and can provide improved image resolution. However, it is limited to small peripheral lesions and has a high false positive rate due to increased sensitivity which comes from high scatter rejection capabilities. As a result, spiral CT may lead to unnecessary interventional procedures.

Optical imaging involves probing tissue with non-ionizing radiation in the visible and near-infrared region (400nm-1500nm). Studying the optical properties of tissue reveals information that can potentially characterize diseases [2-4]. It can provide metabolic information combined with anatomical information which enhances the detection process of early cancer. White light bronchoscopy (WLB), auto-fluorescence imaging (AFI) and narrow-band imaging (NBI), high magnification bronchovideoscopy, endobronchial ultrasound (EBUS) and optical coherence tomography (OCT) are currently used optical imaging techniques that have been developed to enhance the ability to diagnose NSCLC at a pre-invasive stage. Most peripheral tumors are adenocarcinomas or large cell carcinomas. Because of their peripheral location, adenocarcinomas may not be caught early until they have developed extrathoracic metastases. For example, patients may show clinical signs of bone spread or intracranial metastatic disease. On the other hand, squamous cell carcinoma of the central airway is thought of as a multistep process starting from a squamous metaplasia, which progresses to dysplasia, followed by carcinoma in situ (CIS), finally progressing to invasive cancer.

Earlier works on early lung cancer detection include interrogation of living epithelial cells based on light scattering spectroscopy with polarized light which has been reported by [5]. In that specific methodology, both single backscattering from the uppermost epithelial cells and multiply scattered light have been obtained, but the index of refraction and size distribution of the epithelial cells were assessed through single backscattering.

In another study by Backman et al [6], a method for selective detection of size-dependent scattering characteristics of epithelial cells in vivo based on polarized illumination and polarization sensitive detection of scattered light was presented. The finding of that study revealed that reflectance spectroscopy with polarized light can provide quantitative morphological information which could potentially be used for non-invasive detection of neoplastic changes.

In another study, by combining both wavelength-dependent and polarization-dependent methods, changes in light scatter were measured [7]. The outcome of that study revealed that the difference in scattering is attributed to the average dimension of the “scatterers”, being a few tens of nanometers smaller in the healthy cells compared with the cancerous cells.

Finally, classification of cultured human lung cancer cells has been performed by [11] using Raman spectroscopy, principal component analysis (PCA), and linear discrimination analysis (LDA). Raman spectra of single, normal lung cells, along with four cancer cells with different pathological types, were successfully obtained .

To the authors’ knowledge, the first polarimetric study of lung cancer tissue interrogation using infrared photons has been reported by [8]-[9]. The study was performed under backscatter geometry and it was concluded that different types of early-stage cancers can be differentiated, based on their distinct polarimetric signatures. In this study, transmitted signal from healthy cells, squamous carcinoma cells, adenocarcinoma cells and a mixture of squamous and adenocarcinoma cells were obtained under sixteen different polarization states corresponding to different polarization selections in the generator and analyzer arms. Cancer changes at cell level occur in the shape, size, and orientation of the nuclei, in an increase in nucleus chromatin content, in variations in the nucleus-cytoplasmatic ratio, and in changes in the cytosolic content [15]. Indeed major morphological changes lead to an increase in the total yield of cells, as well as thickening of the epithelial layer. The outcome of this study indicates that enhanced discrimination of different types of lung cancer cell stages can be achieved based on their polarimetric characteristics, which depend upon the size of the nuclei and the nucleus-cytoplasmatic ratio.

II. THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS

The linear depolarization ratio (LDR) is the ratio expressed as the ratio of the two linearly polarized optical

powers incident on the receiver when the source is also linearly polarized, namely,

$$LDR = \frac{I_{\perp_sample}}{I_{\square_sample}} . \quad (1)$$

Here, I_{\square_sample} is the intensity of the co-polarized state where maximum intensity is obtained and I_{\perp_sample} is the intensity of the cross-polarized state where the minimum intensity is obtained. The concept of residual intensity (R.I.) was introduced by [6] in an effort to extract signatures of the cellular structures. This requires detection of a signal transmitted from the epithelium over a background signal, mainly a diffuse reflectance originating from deeper tissue layers. In our case, the relative change of refractive index of cell structures is small, while the penetration depth in the cell substantially exceeds the epithelial thickness; as a result, the transmitted light from epithelial nuclei contains background contributions mainly from the underlying microscope slide. Therefore, the concept of residual intensity R.I. was utilized [8], expressed in this study as:

$$R.I. = |I_{\perp_sample} - I_{\square_sample}| . \quad (2)$$

although under this experimental scenario it may be considered superfluous to subtract so small background signals from much larger- magnitude copolarized intensities. The degree of linear polarization (DOLP) is another important optical parameter that can be used to study different samples and differentiate them. Its values is always between 0 and 1 and it is given by,

$$DOLP = \frac{|I_{\perp_sample} - I_{\square_sample}|}{|I_{\perp_sample} + I_{\square_sample}|} = \frac{R.I.}{|I_{\perp_sample} + I_{\square_sample}|} . \quad (3)$$

III. EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN

A. Calibration Technique:

The experiment was performed using electronically controlled liquid crystal (LC) retarders and rotators. These were used to control the polarization states of the beam electronically. This was achieved by applying a voltage to the devices. With no voltage applied, the molecules lie parallel to the surface and maximum retardance is achieved. As the voltage is applied across the liquid layer, the molecules rotate towards the direction of the applied electric field, which introduces retardance such that different polarization states are achieved. The liquid crystal devices include a controller, which helps to provide a square wave with changing amplitude that adjusts the retardation. The controller also includes a driver and small VI’s to interface

the devices with LabVIEW. The calibration was performed by a two-step procedure.

1) *Voltage Calibration of Liquid Crystal Retarders And Rotators*: The polarimetric platform was first aligned. The calibrated voltages for the rotator and the retarder in the generator arm were then obtained. This was done by first calibrating the generator arm and then calibrating the analyzer arm. The calibration was obtained by adding each component one by one. Appropriate rotation or retardation for all the states was achieved by applying voltages to the devices. The calibrated states were the different polarization states: Horizontal (H), Vertical (V), $+45^\circ$ linear (P), -45° linear (M), Right circular (RCP) and Left circular (LCP).

Calibration was obtained by using a method called Null-Intensity Method where the analyzer polarizer was always kept cross-polarized to the generator polarizer and a voltage was applied to each of the LC devices such that the null intensity was obtained [13]. Because of the presence of some system noise in the experiment, the true null was difficult to observe using this method for alignment. Thus, a different method was used for calibration. For this, the analyzer polarizer was rotated by small angle $\Delta\theta$ to measure the intensities at $90^\circ + \Delta\theta$ and $90^\circ - \Delta\theta$. When these two measurements were equal, the null exactly midway between these angles was the calibration voltage. The measurements were repeated until the two equal measurements were obtained. This method is known as Method of Swings [14]. The calibration setup for the system is as shown in Fig 1.

Figure 1. System Calibration Setup

2) *Calibration using known targets with known Mueller matrix (Accuracy Test)*: After the liquid crystal devices (retarders and rotators) were calibrated, these calibration voltages were first tested using some components of known Mueller matrix.

The components used were air, Linear Horizontal Polarizer, i.e., a polarizer having its transmission axis in the horizontal direction (LHP), and Linear Vertical Polarizer, i.e., a polarizer having its transmission axis in the vertical direction. These test experiments were done in transmission mode, i.e., placing the generator and the analyzer arm in the line-of-sight. Between the generator and the analyzer arm, the object to be tested was placed. For air, no object is needed. The polarizers (linear horizontal and vertical) used for the experiment were specified for the wavelength range of 700nm to 1100nm which is within the range of the laser that was being used (1060 nm). The experimental setup for

the test is similar to that one shown in Fig.1 except that the object to be tested is inserted between the generator arm and the analyzer arm. The plots of the ideal and experimentally obtained Mueller matrix intensities of three calibration targets are plotted in Fig. 2.

2-a

2-b

2-c

Figure 2. Comparison of ideal and experimental Mueller matrix intensities of a) air; b) a linear horizontal polarizer (LHP); and c) a linear vertical polarizer

B. Experimental Arrangement and Measurements:

1) *Histological Preparation and Description:* Different histological subtypes of non-small-cell lung cancer were utilized in this study: NCI-H292 cells are human lung bronchiolar epithelial cells derived from human stage-2 squamous cell carcinoma (Grade 1 well-differentiated tumors); A549 cells are human lung alveolar basal epithelial cells derived from human acinar adenocarcinoma with gland formation (Grade 2 poorly/moderately differentiated tumors). The mixed sample contains 50% of NCI-H292 cells and 50% of A549 cells.

In this experiment, four different human lung cells samples were studied: a) normal human lung fibroblast cell (WI-38) line, used as a reference; b) human lung squamous cell carcinoma cell (NCI-H292) line; c) human lung adenocarcinoma cell (A549) line; d) mixture of human lung squamous cell carcinoma cell (NCI-H292) line and human lung adenocarcinoma cell (A549) line. All cell lines were thawed, cultured in DMEM medium (WI-38 cells and A549 cells) and RPMI-1640 medium (NCI-H292 cells) with 10% heat-inactivated FBS (Hyclone, Logan, UT), 100 units/ml penicillin, 100 μ g/ml streptomycin in 5% CO₂ cell culture incubator at 37°C. After 2 passes when they reached the log phase of growth, all four types of samples were seeded into 2-well cell culture slides (BD Falcon) in complete media at the concentration of 1.0×10^5 cells/well. After 24 hours incubation, cell monolayers grown on cell culture slide were rinsed twice with PBS, fixed with paraformaldehyde (4%) according to standard protocol.

The morphological characteristics of the above cell lines are the following: **a) human lung fibroblast cell (WI-38) line:** cell diameter: $50.0 \pm 3.0 \mu\text{m}$; nucleus diameter: $25 \pm 3 \mu\text{m}$; **b) human lung squamous cell carcinoma cell (NCI-H292) line:** cell diameter: $20.0 \pm 3.0 \mu\text{m}$; nucleus diameter: $17 \pm 3 \mu\text{m}$; **c) human lung adenocarcinoma cell (A549) line:** cell diameter: $50.0 \pm 3.0 \mu\text{m}$; nucleus diameter: $10 \pm 3 \mu\text{m}$; and **d) a 50:50 mixture of human lung squamous cell carcinoma cell (NCI-H292) line and human lung adenocarcinoma cell (A549) line.**

2) Polarimetric System Description

Experiments were performed under transmission geometry using the US AFRL Polarimetric Multifunctional Imaging Platform (Fig. 3). The imaging system contained two branches; a polarization generating branch and a polarization analyzing branch. Light from a 1065-nm laser source operating at a pulse repetition rate (PRR) of 200 Hz was sent through the polarization generating branch, consisting of a linear polarizer P1 set at $+45^\circ$, a liquid crystal rotator with fast axis at 135° and a liquid crystal retarder with fast axis at 45° , so that that linearly polarized waves maintained their initial polarization state.

Figure 3. Experimental arrangement under transmission geometry utilizing the US AFRL Polarimetric Multifunctional Imaging Platform

Optical pulses of 1065 nm wavelength and <40 ps pulse duration were generated through a PiLas laser diode system and transmitted through monolayer lung cancer cells deposited on a glass slide (1.2 mm thickness) and then detected after passing through the analyzer arm. Specifically, the analyzer arm consisted of a liquid crystal retarder with fast axis at 45° , a liquid crystal rotator with fast axis at 45° and a linear polarizer at -45° which were placed in front of a New Focus 2151 femtowatt photodetector. The photodetector has a 1 mm diameter aperture and exhibits an ultra low noise equivalent power (NEP) $\leq 15 \text{ fW/Hz}^{1/2}$, a maximum conversion gain of 1×10^{11} , and a typical responsivity of 0.5 A/W. Optical measurements were obtained at sixteen different polarization states, with a combination of four polarization states in the generator and the analyzer arm. The acquired waveforms with their respective histograms were then recorded using a 7000 Series Lecroy Wave Analyzer, and finally processed using Excel and Matlab subroutines.

IV. DISCUSSION

The accuracy of the calibration voltages had been verified by calculating the Mueller matrix of known test objects and comparing those results with the ideal one. The plots of Fig. 2 indicate excellent agreement between theory and experiment for selected known test objects. As result, the liquid crystal retarders and rotators were calibrated accurately at different polarization states and hence could be used for the experimental analysis of the cancer cell samples. Using the experimental arrangement of Fig. 3, repeatability experiments took place aimed at assessing the stability of the polarimetric system (Fig. 4). The stability of the polarimetric system was assessed by performing six repetitious measurements of copolarized detected intensities over a time period of 8.04 minutes. By inspecting Fig. 4, it is observed that the polarimetric system exhibited excellent stability over time.

Figure 4. Repeatability experiments under co-polarized geometry

In Fig. 5 and 6, measurements of detected amplitudes of transmitted signal contributions under co-polarized and cross-polarized geometries are reported. Then the residual intensity plot for healthy lung cell, squamous carcinoma, adenocarcinoma and the mixture of squamous and adenocarcinoma is shown in Fig. 7, while in Fig. 8, the linear depolarization ratio of different lung cancer cells is shown which has been calculated. Finally, the DOLP has been estimated from the residual intensity and plotted in Fig.9.

Figure 5. Intensities of different samples under copolarized geometry

Figure 6. Intensities of different samples under cross-polarized geometry

The experimental results of this study indicate that the transmitted polarimetric signal intensities through healthy lung cell are higher than those from squamous carcinoma and adenocarcinoma cells, as shown in Fig. 4 and 5. Similarly, the polarized residual intensity is higher in healthy lung cells than the cancer cells (Fig. 7); in addition, the squamous carcinoma maintains more the polarization of the incident light than the adenocarcinoma, while the depolarization ratio of the healthy lung cell is less than that the depolarization ratio of both carcinoma cells (Fig. 8). Based on the plots of Fig. 9, the degree of linear polarization is higher in healthy lung cells than lung cancer cells. Again, the light transmitted by squamous carcinoma cells is more highly linearly polarized than that transmitted by adenocarcinoma cells. The above observations can be interpreted based on the fact that fibroblast cells (healthy cells) maintain the polarization of the incident light, while epithelial cell cancers depolarized the light. By referring to the cancer cells, it is observed that smaller size nuclei, large nucleus-cytoplasmic ratio (squamous carcinoma) tend to enhance polarization which respect to larger nuclei, smaller nucleus-cytoplasmic ratio (adenocarcinoma). These observations would indirectly highlight the importance of intracellular matrix surrounding the nuclei, including the mitochondria as key-scattering centers and their tendency to depolarize light.

It is also observed that the optical properties of the mixture of squamous carcinoma and adenocarcinoma always lie between the properties of squamous carcinoma and adenocarcinoma. It is interesting that Fig. 7 for R.I. looks exactly like Figs. 5 and 6 for co-polarized intensity. This is because the depolarization ratio (Fig. 8) is very small (<0.035) for all samples. It is also noted that signals you are looking for the DOLP and their differences is quite large (93-96%) and varies by only ~3% between the samples. Both of these mean that the polarization between samples is quite small, requiring careful attention to experimental details.

Figure 7. Residual Intensity of different cancer cells compared to normal cells

Figure 8. Linear Depolarization Ratio of different cancer cells

Figure 9. Degree of Linear Polarization (DOLP) of different cancer cells

V. CONCLUSION

The outcome of this study indicates that enhanced discrimination between different types of lung cancer cell stages can be achieved based on their polarimetric characteristics which depend upon the size of the nuclei and the nucleus-cytoplasmatic ratio.

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